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Executive Summary

Historic buildings have an inestimable value and provide a sense of identity for cities and their inhabitants. Challenging environmental conditions, natural occurrences, human activities and the indoor microclimate of such structures significantly impact the preservation of artifacts within these spaces (Aste N. et al, 2019). Environmental parameters, such as temperature, relative humidity and light, should be kept as constant as possible, avoiding abrupt variations (UNI, 1999).

During the last decades, many studies were carried out for several types of buildings (churches, museums, collections, deposits, etc.), to identify best practices to keep conservation conditions stable. This deliverable focuses on IoT-based solutions for sustainable environmental monitoring, aiming to analyze microclimates of the *Chiesa della Misericordia* in L'Aquila and their impact on the recently discovered frescoes. Therefore, in line with the themes of Spoke 5, this Church represents, for its specificity, the ideal framework for developing an experimental approach to monitoring environmental parameters.

Taking into account the state of art about ICTs and the Internet of Things (IoT) applied to cultural heritage prevention, this contribution proposes a structured methodology of a sensor network and prefigures its potential outcomes. It represents the first phase of the ongoing broader research aimed to create a centralized control room, where data from multiple sites on urban scale will converge, activating an alert system when specific parameters exceed optimal preservation conditions.

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Introduction

Indoor environmental conditions significantly impact cultural heritage artifacts, particularly in historical sites, museums, galleries, and archives where sensitive artworks are stored and displayed. Poor air quality can lead to the degradation of these items, affecting their longevity and historical value. Moreover, the indoor microclimate of such historic sites plays a significant role in the conservation of the finishing, the construction elements and the artifacts contained in such spaces (Aste N. et al, 2019), and with particular reference to the artworks they contain (paintings, frescoes, sculptures, wooden panels, sacred objects, furnishings, organs, etc.) (Aste N. et al, 2016). Traditional methods of monitoring indoor air quality in cultural heritage settings are often insufficient due to their inability to provide real-time data or continuous monitoring.

By incorporating Internet of Things (IoT) technology, institutions can ensure the optimal conditions for artifact preservation, prevent deterioration, and improve the management of indoor environments. Institutions can continuously monitor key environmental parameters such as temperature, humidity, CO₂, particulate matter, and volatile organic compounds using IoT sensors in museums, galleries, historical buildings, and storage rooms. These real-time insights can enable proactive measures to protect sensitive items from degradation caused by fluctuating air quality. Automated systems can adjust climate controls, lighting, and ventilation based on real-time data, reducing the risk of irreversible damage to artifacts. Additionally, IoT solutions help optimize energy use, improve conservation efforts, and ensure healthier environments for both collections and visitors, ultimately preserving cultural heritage for future generations.

In this deliverable, we will consider an effective and affordable solution for monitoring a specific historic site, the Church of Santa Maria della Misericordia in L'Aquila. In the context of the *Misericordia* Church in L'Aquila, the discovery of 16th-century frescoes of extraordinary value transformed a technical intervention into a meaningful contribution to all community. It is one of the most significant restorations of the post-

earthquake reconstruction of L'Aquila, for the discovery's importance and its impact among art history scholars. This site and its valuable frescoes necessitate a comprehensive and innovative approach to be monitored and safeguarded. Moreover, for its planimetric and elevation specificities (Fig.1), the *Chiesa della Misericordia* represents an ideal framework for developing a precise, consistent, and replicable methodology for monitoring the microclimatic and environmental conditions in spaces where such decorative ensembles are preserved.

Fig.1. The Church of Santa Maria della Misericordia; the photo, during restoration, shows the single hall space that characterises the church, with rich frescoes rediscovered and partly visible on the sides.

Therefore, this deliverable focuses on IoT solutions for long-term environmental monitoring to analyze and preserve the church's microclimate and its influence on the newly revealed frescoes and decorative apparatuses. This attempts to provide a replicable methodology for monitoring and managing environmental risks, connected with air quality, ensuring the best possible sustainability of cultural heritage, by using a

combination of state-of-the-art sensors and data analytics.

1. State of art of IoT for Cultural Heritage

IoT, which stands for 'Internet of Things', refers to technological development whereby, through the Internet, each object acquires its own identity in the digital world. Therefore, IoT is based on the idea of 'intelligent' objects interconnected with each other in order to exchange the information they possess, collect and/or process. One of the most important applications - which has been growing in recent years - is for monitoring cultural heritage. The environmental assessment of historical structures necessitates a meticulous and well-structured investigation to keep conservation conditions as stable as possible. Notably, European reference standards related to measuring microclimatic parameters in cultural heritage context (EN, 2012) do not prescribe a definitive methodology; rather, they outline general procedures tailored to the particular phenomena under study. In this context, over the years, the examination of historic buildings has employed a variety of methodologies and tools.

IoT infrastructures are coupled with software systems with specific communication protocols that clean, aggregate and publish data from sensors. Today, there are many candidate technologies for the implementation of the indoor sensor network. Some of them offer a wide range of sensors that can be connected to control units (microcontrollers) and programmed with customised software. With this modular 'customisation' we can measure, for example: air quality through the IAQ (indoor air quality) index; air pressure in hPa, humidity in %RH, temperature in °C, combined with other parameters and calculate the final IAQ index. The microcontrollers can be programmed to be brokers or to communicate with an *ad hoc* broker and reuse the entire infrastructure. It is possible, for example, to build an architecture based on a standard publish-subscribe protocol which, using an MQTT (which stands for Message Queuing Telemetry Transport) broker, receives data and stores it in a time series database.

The inclusion of modern ICTs, such as the Internet of Things (IoT), in monitoring the

cultural heritage environments has already shown the huge potential (Maksimović M., Ćosović M., 2019). In particular, it has been used to monitor building structural health, cultural preservation and revitalization, as well as for improving the user experience of the cultural environment (Chianese A., Piccialli F., 2015). Researchers have focused on the development of IoT-based systems for tangible and intangible heritage, demonstrating their versatility in addressing environmental, structural, and data analytics challenges.

In this regard, Maksimović and Ćosović (2019) proposed a three-layer IoT architecture to preserve cultural heritage, specifically focusing on Eastern Orthodox churches' conditions. This system employs modern information and communication technologies (ICT) to monitor and manage environmental factors that can significantly affect the preservation of ancient structures. Similarly, Gribaudo et al. (2017) demonstrated IoT-based monitoring in the UNESCO World Heritage site of Matera, Italy, where sensors were employed to track environmental changes combined with structural ones, allowing authorities to take preventive actions before damage occurred. This research highlighted the importance of IoT solutions in managing large cultural sites with complex environmental and crowd-related dynamics.

In the context of museum management, Chianese and Piccialli (2017) explored IoT to design "smart" museums, where sensors and devices enable the dynamic adjustment of environmental factors such as temperature, humidity, and light intensity to optimize artifact preservation. Their work emphasized the challenges of designing a unified IoT architecture that integrates diverse technologies and services to create intelligent museum spaces. The study also highlighted a case of temporary art exhibitions in the Maschio Angioino Castle in Naples, Italy, where IoT played a crucial role in improving the management of exhibitions and safeguarding cultural objects.

Beyond environmental monitoring, IoT has been explored for predictive analytics in cultural heritage preservation. Perles et al. (2020) introduced an energy-efficient IoT architecture aimed at preventive conservation. Their solution utilized low-impact sensor technologies such as LoRa and Sigfox, which were designed for long-lasting monitoring with minimal impact on the artifacts. This scalable architecture integrates cloud-based processing to analyze and visualize data, supporting proactive conservation

strategies for diverse cultural heritage environments. Moreover, Piccialli et al. (2020) examined how IoT-generated data, particularly behavioral data from museum visitors, can be leveraged through data science and analytics techniques to enhance museum management and improve visitor engagement.

Another significant development in this field is IoT combined with machine learning techniques for the predictive modeling of cultural heritage sites. Lee W. and Lee D. (2019) explored the potential of advanced IoT data analytics, including deep learning models such as LSTM and GRU, to predict and prevent damage to cultural monuments. Their research focused on the Woljeong Bridge in South Korea, showing how recurrent neural networks (RNNs) can utilize time-series IoT data to anticipate structural issues, thus facilitating timely interventions and ensuring long-term preservation.

In conclusion, integrating IoT technologies in this field means proving to be a promising approach for enhancing the sustainability and resilience of heritage sites. From environmental monitoring and smart museum designs to predictive analytics for preventive conservation, IoT is becoming a critical tool for safeguarding cultural assets in the face of increasing environmental and human-induced challenges.

2. Methodology

Methodologically, we start from a basic assumption: while monitoring through IoT solutions is regularly practiced in museums, as a result of several available protocols, far more unexplored remains the monitoring of indoor and outdoor cultural sites scattered throughout the territories.

Museums, in fact, pay extreme attention to optimal conservation conditions of the spaces and environments in which the artworks are exhibited and preserved. Each museum is required to guarantee the public's right to access and enjoy their collections, but it also has the duty to constantly monitor the most critical environmental parameters for conservation: light parameters (lux and UV) and thermo-hygrometric ones. If this requires in Museums a great effort by the professionals involved (custodians, curators, conservators, restorers), it often becomes practically impossible

in the case of the cultural heritage scattered throughout the territory. The project presented here starts from this basic consideration: all cultural heritage is worthy of equal attention and care, through monitoring.

Fig. 2. A detail of one of the niches, in which it's visible the fragmentation of the space, under baroque overlays.

In order to do this, measurements must be taken over a period of time that allows for a sufficiently in-depth knowledge of the time course of the values of the quantities themselves at the various significant points in space. The spaces of the Misericordia church in particular, due to its articulated 'reconstruction' history (Fig. 2), present a complexity of situations that must be constantly kept under control,

especially for the presence of frescoes that are in the original state of conservation, dating back to the 16th century (Fig. 3-4).

Precisely, because of its complexity, it is not possible to begin from a methodological standard of references, because monitoring systems are usually developed starting from the study of each particular case; for the same reasons, we assume that this work cannot establish a universally valid standard. However, we can aim to draft a monitoring protocol that could be applied to similar types of historical sites, although with the necessary adjustments to take into account the specificities of each individual case.

In the case of the Misericordia, in order to conduct a sufficiently detailed assessment of the environmental conditions within these fragmented spaces, the intention is to equip the environments (the niches, the nave, and the "sacristies," which once corresponded to the arms of the transept) with monitoring devices (sensors) for measuring physical parameters significant to air quality (cf. UNI 1082900, 1999).

To achieve this, we considered the variety of microclimatic conditions observed in the

area, as well as the diverse distribution of the works of interest within the spaces.

Figg. 3 and 4. The same fresco representing *The Espousal of St Catherine*, before (left) and after (right) restoration.

On a general level, we identified sensors with characteristics appropriate for the accuracy required in monitoring, but not excessively detailed in data collection, both for data management purposes and to avoid significant cost implications. This approach aims to make the project potentially replicable, even by public offices and heritage conservation agencies. On an applicative level, thanks to the collaboration of a team comprising physicists, technologists, computer scientists, art historians, and conservation experts, a detailed analysis of the site and of its conservation issues was initiated. The project concerning the Misericordia church, therefore, aims to address specific questions:

- Which are the most critical points of conservation?
- Is it possible to assure methods and sensors positions to best respect the aesthetic and decorative values (even the cultic ones) of the asset in its complexity?
- Which are the physical quantities that mostly impact on the conservation of these valuable frescoes?

2.1 Why monitor environmental parameters in this case

Monitoring is both necessary and urgent for the Misericordia Church, due to the rediscovery of the frescoes, which were previously literally sealed by a wall dating back to the time of the church's Baroque redecoration (early 18th century). This circumstance makes the condition of these frescoes - probably unprecedented - in the history of conservation, because:

1) they have returned to their original appearance (free from the overlays often found in layers due to multiple restoration interventions);

2) they are now exposed (after 500 years!) to atmospheric and climatic conditions that were entirely absent at the time of their creation and up until their coverage in the first half of the 18th century;

3) that the restoration project director has - correctly - chosen to leave visible (as seen in Fig. 2) the building's construction stratifications, means that, within the niches, unique microclimatic conditions may arise, in contrast to the macroenvironment of the single-nave church.

2.2 Long-Term Monitoring Approach

Given the delicate nature of the frescoes and the unique microclimatic conditions in the niches described above, a **long-term monitoring methodology** was selected to capture consistent environmental data over an extended period. In order to do this, it is first necessary to start with a preliminary phase, and then initiate this long-term monitoring. This makes it possible to identify the points of greatest interest and most eloquent in terms of data quality and clarity, for the highest level of information with the smallest possible number of sensors. For this phase, it is necessary to continue this interdisciplinary work with diverse professionals.

2.3 Monitoring Tools

The following sensors are being selected in compliance with heritage conservation standards:

- **Thermo-hygrometers** to track temperature and relative humidity.
- **Surface thermometers** to detect temperature variations of walls that serve as

support for frescoed surfaces. It is not easy to identify suitable sensors, because they are not very widespread, but naturally - when identified - they would be placed on portions of the wall devoid of historical-artistic decorations, but neighboring, adjacent or contiguous to the frescoed walls for direct readings on frescoed walls.

- **Photometers** to measure light exposure.
- **PMx sensors** to assess pollution and contamination risks.
- **Electronic people counters**, enabling correlations between human activity and environmental changes.

In the following image, we show the first prototype assembly that was made specifically for the Misericordia church: it is an aggregation of sensors of several types and with which the very first surveys were carried out.

Fig. 5. First sensor board (approximately 25 cm x 30 cm in size). Currently, the device only detects data, without transmitting or storing them.

The system in the picture, includes:

- **an air quality sensor**, which measures IAQ (indoor air quality) index, air pressure in hPa, humidity in %RH and temperature in °C. IAQ index and humidity values are temperature compensated. In particular, the IAQ index is a measurement for the quality of air. To calculate the IAQ index the Bricklet detects ethane, isoprene, ethanol, acetone and carbon monoxide by adsorption. These gas measurements are combined with the measurements of air pressure, humidity and temperature to calculate the final IAQ index.
- **a CO₂ sensor** that can be used to measure CO₂ concentration from 400 to 10000 ppm (parts per million). It has a high accuracy of ±30 ppm (full-scale) and ±3% (of reading) and it measures temperature and humidity for compensation.
- **a sound pressure sensor**, capable of measuring sound pressure level and sound spectrum. The measured sound pressure level can be returned weighted by the frequency-weighting standards A, B, C, D, ITU-R 468 and flat weighting (Z). The sensor measures loudness of music, construction sites, street noises and other environmental noises in a variety of weighting standards. It is also possible to determine the frequency composition (spectrum). Precisely, it: measures sound pressure level in dB(A/B/C/D/Z) and ITU-R 468; measures the spectrum up to 512 bins and up to 80 samples per second; frequency range 40Hz to 40960Hz; background noise 30 dB, maximum 120 d.
- **a particulate matter sensor** that can be used to measure particulate matter concentration in $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$ for different sizes. It is made of an integrated fan for air flow and distinguishable particle sizes: PM1, PM2.5 and PM10. This makes monitoring particularly relevant 'during restoration', as critical air quality conditions could arise for both operators and works.
- **an ambient light sensor**, which measures ambient light up to 64000 lux, has a full dynamic range from 0.01 lux to 64000 lux and an output in 0.01

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lux steps. The measured illuminance can be read in lux. Thanks to configurable events, it is possible to react to changes in illuminance without polling. Typical applications are illuminance-dependent switching of backlights, motors, etc., but it is also of interest for cultural heritage, particularly for the conservation of rediscovered frescoes.

- an **IMU** (Inertial Measurement Unit) **sensor**, equipped with a 3-axis accelerometer, magnetometer (compass) and gyroscope and works as an inertial measurement unit. It can measure 9 degrees of freedom and computer quaternions, linear acceleration, gravity vector as well as independent heading, roll and pitch angles. It is a complete attitude and heading reference system. It is factory calibrated, and it has an automatic continuous self-calibration during operation.

2.4 Sensor Installation and Data Transmission

For the first installation of the sensors (preliminary phase), the restoration site currently underway in this church is particularly useful, as this allows for various tests to be carried out and for direct and constant dialogue with restorers at work. Thus:

- Sensors are going to be installed in a provisional setup across the church, focusing on the fresco niches and areas prone to environmental variability.
- Data from sensors will be transmitted via a wireless network to a cloud-based control system for storage, analysis, and visualization.

2.5 Data Analytics and Visualization

Here we propose an example of visualization of data from environmental sensors. The data shown in the following image were collected through the installation of monitoring stations in L'Aquila. The data is transmitted via a LORAWAN communication network, installed by GSSI, which routes the data to a server.

Fig. 6. Grafana is a cross-platform open source tool for analyzing and visualizing graphs and diagrams

The same kind of infrastructure could be used to monitor cultural heritage sites. The collected data will be processed using low-code development platforms (LCDPs). LCDPs support the easy development of IoT solutions and data processing. These data are also being processed using machine learning models to identify trends, predict potential risks, and generate actionable insights. A centralized control room was established, displaying real-time visualizations for stakeholders, including conservation specialists and urban planners.

The following figures show the very first measurements conducted in the central nave of the church, specifically within the church's apse. In the following image, the sensor board setup is displayed: at the top of the interface, it is possible to select a specific sensor to monitor real-time data. (Fig. 7-8-9-10-11-12).

Fig.7. Measurement through air quality sensor

Fig.8. Measurement through CO₂ sensor

Fig.9. Measurement through sound pressure sensor

Fig.10. Measurement through particulate matter sensor

Fig.11. Measurement through ambient light sensor

Fig.12. Measurement through IMU sensor

Although the data were collected within a short period of time and therefore they are not perfectly suited for monitoring the overall conservation state of the Misericordia Church, this initial measurement served to assess the potential of this sensor infrastructure over the long term.

3. Results

3.1 Environmental Monitoring Metrics

Preliminary environmental analysis, in collaboration with restorers, in the *Chiesa della Misericordia* allow to assume with good approximation that the church and its indoor spaces are affected (fig. 5) by significant variations in microclimatic parameters, particularly in the small niches housing the frescoes. The monitored variables included:

- **Temperature fluctuations** (daily and seasonal cycles).
- **Relative humidity** is crucial for controlling condensation and mold growth.
- **Surface temperature and humidity** critical for detecting material degradation.
- **Light intensity**, to assess risks related to photo-degradation.
- **Human presence**, correlated with environmental changes using an electronic people counter.

3.2 Correlation among parameters

Given the possibility of monitoring the rooms during the restoration, we would also like to investigate the possible correlation between certain elements:

- whether increased human presence during the hours of the restoration site is correlated with peaks in temperature and humidity.
- whether peaks in seasonal humidity would, in the long term, increase stress and/or cause damage to the constituent materials of the fresco, evidenced by alterations to the surface.

- whether the intensity of light, vibration levels due to other construction sites in the vicinity and the consequent passage of heavy vehicles, as well as the strong vibrations due to demolition work, pose potential risks to the frescoes. In particular, strong vibrations could entail the risk of detachment on the base plasters of the frescoes in the sacristies, which are already in a rather precarious state of conservation (Fig. 13).

Fig. 13. The scene of the *Immaculate Conception* in the sacristy (ex transept) on the left, which presents various conservation problems .

3.3 Key Outcomes

The long-term data will provide actionable insights for real-time adjustments to restoration and maintenance activities, such as optimizing ventilation and limiting light

exposure. With this purpose, we intend to develop an Alert system that activates when parameters exceed thresholds, allowing preventive interventions to minimize degradation risks. All the data could converge to a **Control room** and made available to professionals/stakeholders/etc. via a website for remote viewing. Information from multiple sites across the historic city of L'Aquila could gradually be integrated.

Additionally, remotely controlled devices (e.g. room dehumidifiers) can be included in the network in order to automate corrective actions related to the received alarms, from monitored sites. The final system of the control room and of the data flow is currently being designed.

Finally, this initiative aligns with broader goals of fostering an interdisciplinary approach to risk prevention, ensuring cultural heritage sustainability, and enhancing public engagement with restored sites.

3.4 Future Implications: a Control Room

Fig. 14. Example of a map of the city - First level

The case study of the *Chiesa della Misericordia* is part of the broader project the GSSI is carrying out, regarding the establishment of a Control room, planned to be set up in GSSI laboratory. This room is going to receive data collected by sensors installed in the most vulnerable sites of the historic center of L'Aquila. These sensors, able to monitor various environmental, physical, and chemical parameters, will serve to identify and assess the associated risks on both urban and small-scale level. They will be installed both outdoors and indoors to define the general climatic and environmental conditions for risk mitigation actions to be implemented. The sensor network must be capable of continuously measuring parameters such as temperature, humidity, wind, solar radiation, airborne particles and tourist flows. An Alert system in the Control room will activate when parameters exceed optimal thresholds for preservation, ensuring timely intervention. The data gathered at the *Chiesa della Misericordia* could be extended to other historical sites in L'Aquila, contributing to a city-wide network of IoT-enabled heritage monitoring systems.

To this regard, a configuration of the historic city of L'Aquila is going to be created and displayed in the Control Room, on which it will be possible to select the site of interest, read the data from the sensor's installation on-site or any other dedicated instruments, and display it in real time, preserving its temporal trend (see Figure 14).

The map could be structured on three levels: on the first one, a city map will be displayed, highlighting the main sites where monitoring analyses are conducted. On the second level, a detailed 3D map of the site interior will be shown, including data from the installed sensors (see Figure 15 as examples of display). On a potential third level, it could be useful to analyze a specific work of art located within the site to assess its current state of conservation.

Fig. 15. Example of 3D map of a building (in this case a GSSI floor) - Second level

Fig. 16. Alternative for the second level display: a) development of the average humidity value, b) one specific humidity and temperature KPI, and c) layout of the available rooms in the example of GSSI building.

Finally, this initiative aligns with broader goals of fostering an interdisciplinary approach to risk prevention, ensuring cultural heritage sustainability, and enhancing public engagement with restored sites.

Conclusions

The implementation of IoT solutions for microclimatic and environmental monitoring at the *Church of Santa Maria della Misericordia* underscores the pivotal role that advanced technologies play in conservation and preservation of cultural heritage sites. Through the integration of IoT systems, this project could significantly contribute to the safeguarding of the church's structure and artworks by providing real-time alerts and long-term data about various environmental factors, such as temperature, humidity, air quality, etc. The tools at our disposal, specifically selected among those commercially available (COTs), with the minimum of encumbrance and with the utmost respect for the *decorum* of the heritage (including sacred heritage), could help to ensure, in the long-term, the maintenance of optimal conditions for its preservation and its transmission to future generations.

The project also greatly emphasizes the importance of collaboration between different professionals, where they all contribute to the solution that best balances the various aspects of conservation, data collection, monitoring and prevention, but also does not affect the enjoyment and aesthetic beauty of the property. A truly interdisciplinary collaboration.

The project aims to achieve a conservation support, with real-time alerts and data analysis to mitigate environmental risks to the frescoes and decorative elements; finally, the project could establish a replicable methodology to be adapted in other case studies: with tools that are inexpensive and within the reach of even public offices or other research groups, this approach to a site undergoing restoration could be useful to reapply in others, especially in post-earthquake urban contexts such as L'Aquila. This model could represent a sustainable strategy for safeguarding cultural heritage in post-disaster contexts.

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